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Fracture mechanics testing of irradiated RPV steels by means of sub-sized specimens

Deliverable D2.3
Fabrication of irradiated specimens

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D.2.3 - Fabrication of irradiated specimens

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¹ **Nature:** R -Document, report; **DEM** -Demonstrator, pilot, prototype; **DEC** -Websites, patent fillings, videos, etc.; **OTHER**; **ETHICS** -Ethics requirement; **ORDP** -Open Research Data Pilot; **DATA** -data sets, microdata, etc.

² **Dissemination level:** **PU** -Public; **CO** -Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

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1 Introduction

FRACTESUS is an Euratom project concerning the utilization of miniature compact tension (mini-CT) specimens in fracture mechanical assessment of metallic materials in the nuclear power context. In particular, the brittle fracture initiation toughness is investigated with Master Curve methodology, standardized by ASTM as test method E1921[1]. The primary objective is to successfully utilize mini-CT specimens in the evaluation of selected materials with nuclear relevance in non-irradiated and irradiated states and thus validate the methodology. Furthermore, the project aims to provide guidelines for later users.

Previous reports in FRACTESUS [2-6] have described the planning phase as well as the initial phase of stakeholder involvement in the project. Furthermore, the fabrication of unirradiated specimens is reported by Arffman and Lappalainen [7]. This report describes the actions taken in the preparation of mini-CT specimens of irradiated materials in terms of design, fabrication, and fatigue pre-cracking.

2 Background

At the beginning of the project, the test matrix for the project was finalized [2]. This included decisions on test materials and participating laboratories in the testing of each material, as well as guidelines on specimen design. The actual investigations in the project started with unirradiated materials in 2021.

All participants in irradiated materials testing are listed in are listed in Table 1, along with their abbreviations. Most of the testing is done in interlaboratory exercises. In Spring 2022, the material for the interlaboratory study of irradiated material was delivered to the participating laboratories. The material, 73W provided by SCK CEN, is outlined in Table 2 and described in detail in [2]. Additionally, two member institutes are investigating further irradiated materials in the project, listed in Table 3.

The interlaboratory study material was cut from a larger piece tested previously, and the cutting is illustrated in Figure 1. Each partner received two specimen blanks with dimensions 10mm x 10mm x 50 mm, Figure 2. The participants were also informed about the orientation of the piece in terms of its original manufacturing. On the other hand, mini-CT specimens from ANP-4 investigated by FRA-G were manufactured from the already tested SE(B) 10x10 specimens. These specimens in turn were taken from a WOL-100X specimen.

Fabrication of specimens was done in accordance with ASTM E1921 standard requirements. In November 2022, participating laboratories were sent a questionnaire on the progress. The template of the form is included in Appendix A.1. As the fabrication of the specimens was still ongoing, the unfinished participants were surveyed again in February 2023 using a similar format. At each point, the participants were enquired for further clarification in an open format.

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Table 1. Research organisations participating in irradiated mini-CT testing in FRACTESUS. It should be noted that EK-CER has changed their abbreviation from MTA-EK.

Institute	Abbreviation	Participation in the interlaboratory study
Studiecentrum voor Kernenergie / Centre d'Étude de l'Énergie Nucléaire	SCK CEN	x
ÚJV Řež, a.s.	NRI	x
Teknologian tutkimuskeskus VTT Oy	VTT	x
Commissariat à l'Énergie Atomique et aux Énergies Alternatives	CEA	x
Helmholtz-Zentrum Dresden-Rossendorf eV	HZDR	x
Energiatudományi Kutatóközpont	EK-CER	x
Nuclear Research and Consultancy Group	NRG	x
Framatome GmbH	FRA-G	

Table 2. Material utilised for irradiated round-robin exercise.

Material	T0	Orientation	Fluence [E19 cm ⁻²] (E > 1 MeV)	No. of tests
73W	+34°C	T-L	1.5 (at ~288°C)	16

Table 3. Test matrix for additional fracture toughness tests of irradiated materials outside the round-robin exercises.

Material	Orientation	T0 [°C]	Fluence [E19 cm ⁻²] (E > 1 MeV)	Participant	No. of tests
15H2MFA		-134	0	EK-CER	16
15H2MFA		> -134	I1	EK-CER	16
15H2MFA		> -134	I2	EK-CER	16
15H2MFA		> -134	IA	EK-CER	16
15H2MFA		> -134	IAI	EK-CER	16
ANP-4	L-S	< -78	3,41	FRA-G	16

Figure 1. Illustration of cutting interlaboratory study material.

Figure 2. Image of interlaboratory material as it was delivered to participants as a specimen blank. Each participant received two such bars, marked L and R. The scale is set at 10 mm.

3 Specimen design

Specimen design was initially covered already in the planning phase and during fabrication of unirradiated specimens, as reported in [2] and [7], respectively. During irradiated specimen fabrication the essential dimensions were surveyed again to account for any changes.

In general, the design was only required to follow the recommendations of ASTM E1921 [1]. During the assessment of the fracture mechanical test results differences between participants' designs are then considered, particularly if test results vary greatly. Table 4 summarizes the essential dimensions of the specimens from each participant, while Table 5 describes the labels used for the dimensions.

Although the designs of different participants are very similar, there are some key takeaways to consider:

- i. SCK CEN utilizes two different specimen designs in the project. While the first one is very similar to the design used by other participants, the second one (SCK CEN II) is slightly larger than the regular, 4 mm thick mini-CT specimen. SCK CEN is investigating two parallel series of specimens from the interlaboratory study material, and possible differences can thus be distinguished. Furthermore, SCK CEN previously utilized the two designs side by side to investigate unirradiated materials.[7]
- ii. The COD measurement location divides participants: Some have gauges attached to the front face (FF) of the specimen, while others mount it on the load-line (LL). The methods are considered equal, but if COD is measured from the front face a rotation correction must be applied during analysis.
- iii. As decided during test matrix planning, the specimens are not side-grooved.
- iv. EK-CER decided to return to front-face clip gauge configuration after their experiences during non-irradiated materials testing. Their primary testing machine is hydraulic, and the hydraulic system may not stop immediately after brittle fracture. If the clip gauge is attached to the mini-CT specimen at load-line from the outside, the continuing movement risks damaging the extensometer. In the front-face configuration, the clip gauge simply falls off. Furthermore, EK-CER were wary of the difference in their results in the non-irradiated round-robin, [8], compared to other participants could be due to their load-line crack opening displacement measurement setup.
- v. The lengths of the machined starter notch a_N vary. A longer starter notch expedited specimen preparation as the fatigue pre-crack required is shorter. However, ASTM E1921 sets some limits for both the machined notch and the fatigue pre-crack. In terms of EDM manufacturing used by all participants, unless a very thin wire is utilized, the pre-crack length requirement related to the height of the machined notch is the most limiting one. If the time consumed by the fatiguing process does not need to be optimized, a shorter machined notch is a safe approach. In any case, the limiting requirements and optimal choices depend on the testing laboratory.

Table 4. Specimen dimensions of the specimens of participating laboratories. The symbols are described in Table 5.

PARTICIPANT	W	W _{TOT}	H	a _N	H*	Δ	D	B
SCK CEN I	8	10	9.6	2.4	2.2	4.3	2	4
SCK CEN II	8.3	10	10	2.3	2.3	4.5	2	4.2
NRI	8	10	9.6	3	2.2	1.5	2	4
VTT	8	10	9.6	3.2	2.25	4.5	2	4
CEA	8	10	9.6	2.4	2.2	1	2	4
HZDR	8	10	9.6	3	2.2	1.5	2	4
NRG	8	10	9.6	3.2	2.2	4.5	2	4
FRA-G	8	10	9.6	2.7	2.2	1.25	2	4

Table 5. Descriptions of specimen dimensions listed in Table 4.

LABEL	DESCRIPTION
W	Specimen width
W_{TOT}	Full width
H	Specimen height
a_N	Length of machined notch
H*	A half span of applied load points
Δ	A half span of displacement measurement points
D	Diameter of loading pinholes
B	Specimen thickness

4 Fabrication of specimens

In general, all participants were successful in the fabrication of the specimens. As with the unirradiated materials, fatigue pre-cracking challenges were the most prevalent. Three participants reported issues related to pre-crack non-uniformity. NRG mentioned that they believe theirs to be related to the clamping/correct alignment of the specimen, which is more challenging under hot cell conditions. Utilization of additional tools to check the specimen alignment in-cell solved the issues for them.

Despite potential challenges related to inhomogeneity of 73W as a weld material and in-cell specimen preparation, fewer problems were encountered by the laboratories during irradiated specimen preparation, compared to the unirradiated materials. Therefore, it seems that issues met during fabrication of non-irradiated specimens had been mostly solved. This illustrates the importance of thorough validation of all steps with inexpensive materials in miniaturized testing, especially considering that irradiated materials are generally much more valuable.

At VTT, the dimensions of the original piece were found to be time-consuming during fabrication. While slicing the specimen blanks into specimens appeared simple, further machining was required to incorporate all the necessary features. This meant that each mini-CT had to be rotated and fixed into position several times, which was challenging due to limited extra material. Moreover, rotations and difficult attachments required considerable care to avoid misalignment, making the fabrication process slower compared to some other forms of the original piece. It's important to consider the difficulty of fabrication, particularly for miniature specimens due to their small size. Ensuring reliable attachment of the specimen can be challenging, and fabrication must be more accurate than that of larger specimens.

In general, the small specimens are challenging to observe during in-cell operation. It is difficult to even see the specimens through the protective lead glass. To notice issues during fabrication, as well as other stages of in-cell work, a well-designed camera system is recommended. Furthermore, technical issues are generally more time-consuming to solve than outside the hot cells, and an additional risk for delays should therefore be considered.

5 Deviations

The work and deliverable are late due to constrained resources at all stages. Furthermore, the current energy crisis has severely limited the operation of one partner. The passing of the project coordinator also caused further delays. These delays, however, are expected to be manageable in terms of general progress of the project.

Due to additional delays at EK-CER, their input will be included as an appendix in deliverable D5.5.

6 Conclusion

In FRACTESUS, the participants are investigating irradiated materials with miniature compact tension specimens. Irradiated specimen fabrication and preparation for fracture mechanical testing commenced in 2022, with most participants finalizing the work by the end of March 2023.

In general, the preparation of irradiated specimens has largely been successful. Some participants reported sporadic non-conformance cases regarding crack front uniformity. However, all issues might not be evident before testing has ended and post-test assessments are finished.

The specimen designs between participants vary. The differences are generally minor, but they are nevertheless considered during evaluation of results. Since the tests are mostly done in interlaboratory exercises, potential differences can be pointed out. Furthermore, the unirradiated materials' investigations support the identification of differences.

The deliverable aims to support further work in FRACTESUS, particularly the assessment of any discrepancies in test results and formulation of general guidelines for mini-CT utilization in fracture toughness evaluation.

7 References

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APPENDICES

A.1. Questionnaire template

In addition to the form below, the participants were asked to provide the essential dimensions and drawings of their specimen designs, as well as specimen cutting plans.

Your name, participating organization	
Have you received all the materials allocated to you in the test matrix?	
Have you started the fabrication of specimens from the materials?	
If not, has there been unexpected issues?	
If yes, have you finished the fabrication?	
Did you encounter any problems/challenges/curiosities?	
Did you have to make any changes to original plans?	
If you have already started fatigue pre-cracking/testing the materials, have you identified any problems/challenges/curiosities related to specimen fabrication?	
Any additional comments?	